

HYPHIEND

Understanding and preventing the impact of endocrine disruptors in sensitive populations

One of the first research projects to study Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals' effects on the hypothalamus-pituitary axis using a multidisciplinary approach, including preclinical models and two European-wide clinical studies.

www.hypiend.eu

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This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No. 101137440. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Understanding and preventing the impact of endocrine disruptors in sensitive populations

One of the first research projects to study Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals' (EDC) effects on the hypothalamus-pituitary axis

www.hypiend.eu

HYPIEND findings will be used to delineate interventional strategies for minimizing EDC exposure and consequences on the neuroendocrine system in pregnant and breastfeeding women and prepubertal children

01
Improve public health

02
Raise consumer awareness on EDCs impacts

03
Protect ecosystems and wildlife

04
Shape government regulations and policies

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